

SPECIMEN SIZE EFFECT ON THE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF CARBON FIBRE-EPOXY LAMINATES CONSIDERING THE INFLUENCE OF THE ANTI-BUCKLING DEVICE

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SUMMARY: The in-plane size effect of specimen gauge section (length \times width) was investigated on the compressive behaviour of a T300/924C [45/-45/0/90]_{3s}, carbon fibre-epoxy laminate. A modified ICSTM compression test fixture was used together with an anti-buckling device to test 3mm thick specimens with a 30 \times 30, 50 \times 50, 70 \times 70 and 90mm \times 90mm gauge length by width section. In all cases failure was sudden and occurred mainly within the gauge length. Post failure examination suggests that 0° fibre microbuckling is the critical damage mechanism that causes final failure. This is a matrix dominated failure mode and its triggering depends very much on initial fibre waviness. It is suggested that manufacturing process and quality may play a significant role in determining the compressive strength. When an anti-buckling device was used to prevent out-of plane deflections, it was observed that the compressive strength of the larger specimens with the device was 6-12% greater than that measured for a 30mm \times 30mm specimens with similar anti-buckling device. This is due to surface larger friction between the specimen and the device. From the analytical results on the influence of the anti-buckling device using finite element method, it was found that the compressive stress calculated with the frictional pressure on the gauge section surface introduced by anti-buckling device was about 7% higher than actual compressive stress. The local stress concentration arising from the hole dominates the strength of the laminate rather than the stresses in the bulk of the material. It is observed that the remote failure stress decreases with increasing hole size and specimen width but is generally well above the value one might predict from the elastic stress concentration factor. This suggests that the material is not ideally brittle and some stress relief occurs around the hole. X-ray radiography reveals that damage in the form of fibre microbuckling and delamination initiates at the edge of the hole at approximately 80% of the failure load and extends stably under increasing load before becoming unstable at a critical length of 2-3 mm (depends on specimen geometry). This damage growth and failure are analysed by a linear cohesive zone model. Using the independently measured laminate parameters of compressive unnotched strength and in-plane fracture toughness the model predicts successfully the notched strength as a function of hole size and width.

KEYWORD: Carbon fibre-epoxy laminate, Compressive testing, Scaling methods, Fibre waviness, Thickness effect

INTRODUCTION

Continuous fibre reinforced plastics have a number of characteristics that are typical to brittle materials. They lack plasticity to reduce the influence of stress concentrations arising from defects, have more or less linear stress-strain curves when loaded in tension or compression along the fibre direction and display significantly more scatter in strength than metallic

materials[1]. In light of these facts, it is natural to ask whether the strength of composites depends on material volume. For instance, the tensile strengths of glass, carbon and aramid filaments, decrease with increasing length [2][3]; the flexural strengths of unidirectional specimens can exceed tensile strengths by as much as 44% and compressive strengths by as much as 56%[4][5]; the flexural strength of 100-ply unidirectional specimens is 15% lower than for 25-ply specimens[6]; the reduction in laminate strength caused by open holes increases with increasing hole size, possibly because the volume of material subjected to a stress concentration increases with increasing hole diameter[7].

Eriksson[9] performed experimental work in order to determine the effect of geometry on the strength with unnotched specimens and open hole specimens loaded in compression, using three different ply orientations (laminate A: $[\pm 45/0_2/90/0_2/90/0_2]_s$, laminate B: $[[\pm 45/90_2/0/90_2/0/90_2]_s$, laminate C: $[\pm 45/0/90]_{3s}$), HTA7/6376. For the width effects of unnotched specimens fabricated using laminate A, he only changed specimen width from 25.4mm to 63.5mm, keeping the same specimen gauge length (50mm) and specimen thickness (2.54mm). It was concluded that there is no specimen width effect without indicating the failure region of the specimens. For open hole specimen testing, he used three different stacking sequences, i.e. laminate A, laminate B and laminate C. The specimens have the same ratio ($a/W=0.25$) of hole diameter (a) to specimen width (W) and their dimensions are same as the unnotched specimens. The test results revealed that the open hole specimen sizes do not influence the failure strength of the open hole composite laminates. However, a hole size effect is generally expected due to the fact that less stable damage and stress distribution in the larger hole specimen is anticipated. These test results are controversial.

Camponeschi investigated compressive strength of different size carbon and glass fibre/epoxy specimens. Unidirectional composites with 48 and 96 plies and cross-ply laminates with layups $(0_2/90)_{ns}$ and 48, 96 and 192 plies were tested. The materials were AS4 and S2 glass fibres with 3501-6 epoxy matrix. The specimen thicknesses, t were 6.35, 12.7 and 25.4mm. The widths were $4t$, and the gauge lengths of most of the specimens were $5t$. Johnson *et al*[1][2]. also carried out compressive tests on cross-ply $([0/90]_{4s}$, $[0_2/90_2]_{4s}$ and $[0/90]_{8s}$) and quasi-isotropic (sublaminate scaled $[45/-45/0/90]_{4s}$ and $[45/-45/0/90]_{8s}$ and ply level scaled $[45_2/-45_2/0_2/90_2]_{2s}$ and $[45_4/-45_4/0_4/90_4]_{2s}$) laminates with all dimensions scaled.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material

The material used was Toray T300 carbon fibre in a Ciba-Geigy 924C epoxy resin (T300/924C). The pre-impregnated tapes (pre-preg) were laid up by hand into a $[45/-45/0/90]_{3s}$ quasi-isotropic lay-up and cured according to the manufacturer's recommended procedure. The quality of the moulded laminates was examined by using ultrasonic C-scanning. The in-plane stiffness and strength of the T300/924C unidirectional laminate are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Stiffness and strength properties for the T300/924C composite system

Property	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	σ_{11C} (MPa)	τ_{12y} (MPa)
Value	164	11	5.7	0.34	1570	64
Coefficient of Variation (%)	6.1	5.35	0.3	5.6	15.8	2.5

(σ_{11C} = longitudinal compressive strength and τ_{12y} = in-plane yield shear strength)

Specimen Geometry

Several specimens were cut from the 3 mm thick panels and woven glass fibre-epoxy reinforcement tabs were bonded giving gauge sections of 30×30 , 50×50 , 70×70 and $90 \text{ mm} \times 90 \text{ mm}$. The geometry of the 30 mm long by 30 mm wide specimen is based on the Airbus Industry test method (AITM-1.008). Circular holes of diameter 1.5 - 36 mm (diameter/width ratio, $a/W = 0.05 - 0.5$) were drilled at the centre of the specimens using a tungsten carbide bit to minimise fibre damage and delamination at the hole boundary. Penetrant enhanced X-ray radiography was used to inspect the quality of drilling, Fig. 1. The tab surfaces and test specimen edges were machined because the flatness of the surfaces and the square end of the specimen is very important for the specimen alignment. A schematic representation of the specimen geometry is given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1: Typical x-ray radiographs illustrating hole quality of specimens used in this study

L = Total specimen length, l_g = gauge length, b = tab length (50mm), W = width, a = hole diameter.

Fig. 2: Unnotched and open hole specimen dimensions

Compressive Testing

Static compressive tests were carried out on a screw-driven Zwick 1488 universal testing machine with a load capacity of 200kN; a crosshead displacement rate of 1 mm/min was used. Load introduction to the specimen was mainly by end loading using a modified ICSTM fixture, Fig. 3. For all $30 \text{ mm} \times 30 \text{ mm}$, $50 \text{ mm} \times 50 \text{ mm}$, $70 \text{ mm} \times 70 \text{ mm}$ and $90 \text{ mm} \times 90 \text{ mm}$ specimens an anti-buckling device similar to that used by Soutis was employed to prevent column buckling, Fig. 4. It contains a window at the device centre, allowing damage around the hole to occur but restraining the specimen from general bending. Frictional effects were minimised by lining the inner faces of the fixture with Teflon tape; the clearance between the anti-buckling device and the specimen face was less than $500 \mu\text{m}$ only for the $30 \text{ mm} \times 30 \text{ mm}$ specimens.

Fig. 3: Modified ICSTM compression test fixture

Fig. 4: Anti-buckling devices used in this study

Several of the tests were interrupted before final failure in order to examine damage growth. Examination was by dye-enhanced X-ray radiography. Zinc iodide solution has been shown

to be an effective penetrant for highlighting damage regions in composite laminates. The location and nature of damage in individual plies was obtained by using the de-ply technique and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The de-ply method was done by burning off most of the resin, while leaving just enough to keep the fibres in position. The resin was burnt off in an appropriately ventilated furnace since the fumes, which were released are toxic. For the multidirectional stacking sequence of T300/924C used in this study it was found that 30 minutes at a temperature of 400°C yielded optimum results. Once the resin had been burnt off the plies were carefully separated with a blade. These were then attached to a plate and then placed in the vacuum chamber of a JEOL JSM T220A scanning microscope, ready to be viewed. It is to be noted that since carbon is a good conductor there was no need to coat the specimens in conductive material once the resin had been removed

COMPRESSIVE TEST RESULTS

The test results obtained include stress-strain curves to failure and post-failure examination of fracture patterns. The stress-strain response, axial stiffness, strength and final failure patterns were studied as a function of specimen gauge section; thickness of all specimens was approximately 3 mm.

Unnotched Specimens

Failure of the unnotched specimens was sudden and occurred mainly within the specimen gauge length regardless of specimens' size, Fig. 5. This may be because the amount of the local deformation in the window, which has an open space, is different from the other area in the anti-buckling device and then the outermost plies $\pm 45^\circ$ can be easily delaminated in the window. Final failure was sudden like other specimens.

From the post failure examination, specimen failure characteristics are similar regardless of the specimen size. The catastrophic failure involved a combination of fibre microbuckling, delamination between 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies and splitting parallel to the fibres and seemed to occur in a crushing failure mode without a global buckling influence in the area where the failure occurred as shown in Fig. 5.

The compressive stress-strain plots of a selected specimen for each size using back-to-back strain gauges are depicted with the ultimate failure stress and strain in Fig. 6 Plots B for the 50mm \times 50mm specimen, C for the 70mm \times 70mm specimen and D for the 90mm \times 90mm specimen are offset by 0.5%, 1.0% and 1.5% strain respectively. It is apparent from the figure that there is very little divergence of surface strains on the compression specimens. The similarity in strain readings confirms that experimentally the specimens were indeed stable and failure was not related to the bending due to the anti-buckling devices.

The axial moduli of the bigger size specimens shown in the figure are not constant but different up to about 21 % when compared with that of the specimen with the 30mm \times 30mm gauge section. In addition, the average strength of the 30mm \times 30mm specimen was approximately 10% lower than that of the bigger size specimens as shown in Table 2. The discrepancies in the strengths and axial moduli can be explained from the anti-buckling device effect. During mounting the anti-buckling device on the specimens, the deformation of the specimens induced by Poisson's effects were not taken into account in the devices except the 30mm \times 30mm specimens, i.e. the bigger size specimens were directly contacted on the anti-buckling device (no gap between the specimens and the anti-buckling devices) and some pressure introduced by bolts' joining torque in the anti-buckling device was applied on the specimens' gauge section surface.

Fig. 5: Overall failure of different size specimen: front view and side view

Fig. 6: Axial compressive stress-strain plots from four different size specimens of T300/924C laminate $[45/-45/0/90]_{3s}$. (A= 30mm \times 30mm, B= 50mm \times 50mm, C= 70mm \times 70mm and D= 90mm \times 90mm specimen)

Table 2: Average compressive failure strengths of multidirectional ($[45/-45/0/90]_{3s}$) unnotched specimens of the T300/924C system

Compressive Strength of Unnotched Specimen				
Test Fixture	Modified ICSTM			
Specimen Size (mm)	30 \times 30	50 \times 50	70 \times 70	90 \times 90
Thickness (mm)	3	3	3	3
Anti-buckling Device	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Average Failure Strength (MPa)	673	736	750	711
Average Failure Strain (%)	1.51	1.43	1.30	1.58
Coefficient of Variation (%)	3.55	4.28	4.86	2.77

Anti-Buckling Device Effect

The specimens are equipped with the anti-buckling device, tightening four bolts in the device as shown in Fig. 7. When the device is mounted on the specimens, except 30mm \times 30mm specimens, i.e. 50mm \times 50mm, 70mm \times 70mm and 90mm \times 90mm specimens, an adequate pre-torque is applied to the bolts in the device in order to induce the specimen's failure to occur within the anti-buckling device windows as explained in the above section.

For the current numerical analysis, the anti-buckling device used for 50mm \times 50mm specimens was selected. The device and simple schematic diagram are presented in Fig. 7 (a) and (b), respectively. The device consists of two steel blocks with 20mm wide and 30mm long open window and four $\frac{1}{4}$ inch (6.35mm) bolts. The pre-torque was measured using a torque wrench during the test and 10 Nm pre-torque was normally applied to each bolt in the current study. The frictional pressure, P_x on the contacting surface between the device and the specimen can be calculated by the following equation:

$$P_x = \mu \frac{F_i m}{A} = \frac{\mu T_b m}{0.2 d_o A} \quad (1)$$

where T_b ($T_b = 0.2 F_i d_0$, where F_i = axial force of the bolts caused by the torque) is an applied torque on the bolts, m is the number of the bolts in the anti-buckling device, A is a contacting area between the specimen and the anti-buckling device and μ is a frictional coefficient.

In the present study, the bolt diameter (d_0), 6.35mm, the number of the bolts (m), 4 and the measured frictional coefficient (μ), 0.245 were substituted to Equation (1) to predict the frictional pressure, P_x . The frictional coefficient was directly measured through the frictional test. As the boundary condition for the analysis, the through-thickness direction deformation (Z axis) was not allowed due to the frictional pressure, P_x as shown in Figure 7 (b). A two-dimensional finite element analysis using the FE77 Package was performed to investigate the anti-buckling device effect.

Fig. 8 shows the stress distribution according to the frictional coefficients along the specimen width at the specimen middle, where the predicted stress (σ_{xx}) is normalized by the applied stress (σ_A). It is noticed from the figure that the stress is decreased with the increasing frictional coefficient and the maximum stresses are yielded within the anti-buckling device window. When the frictional coefficient (0.245) measured in this study is applied, the stress was reduced by 7% at the centre of the specimen when compared to the stress of the specimen on which the anti-buckling device is not equipped. This means that the compressive failure strength increases as much as 7% when the frictional pressure due to the bolts of the anti-buckling device is applied on the specimen. The measured average compressive strengths in Table 2, therefore, have to be corrected by 7%, i.e. 684 MPa for 50mm \times 50mm specimen, 697 MPa for 70mm \times 70mm specimen and 663 MPa for 90mm \times 90mm specimen. Fig. 9 displays the compressive strength predicted by the maximum stress criterion and the corrected compressive strengths

Open Hole Specimens

All specimens failed from the hole in a direction almost perpendicular to the loading axis by emitting a cracking type sound just prior to catastrophic failure. The failure load is decreased as the hole diameter is increased. From the post-failure investigation, the overall mode of final failure of the specimens which have a different hole size was very similar as shown in Fig. 10. Also, these strength results are displayed in Fig. 11, where the notched failure strength σ_n normalised by the corrected unnotched strength σ_{un} (see Fig. 9) of each size is plotted against the hole diameter (a) normalised by the width (W) of the specimen. Strength values are based on the gross sectional area of the test piece.

It is clear from Fig. 11 that the compressive strength is reduced by 30-70% by the presence of the hole. The measured notched strengths are bounded by simple criteria based on notch sensitivity. If the material is ideally notch insensitive (ideally ductile), the failure stress is proportional to net sectional area, while if the material is ideally notch sensitive (brittle) then the plate fails when the local stress at the edge of the hole equals the failure stress of the material (σ_{un}). The notch sensitive curve in Fig. 11 refers to the case of a quasi-isotropic finite plate; the stress concentration factor (SCF) k_t for a finite plate with a hole can be determined either analytically or from a two-dimensional finite element stress analysis. Material orthotropy alters the position of the curve. Since the data points for all specimen configurations tested lay above the notch sensitive curve, the T300/924C system is not ideally brittle and some stress redistribution occurs around the hole before failure. Examination of the damaged laminates reveals that fibre microbuckling in the 0° plies, surrounded by delamination, occurs in the vicinity of the hole prior to catastrophic fracture. The microbuckled zone extends like a line-crack for 2-3 mm along the specimen width before final failure, Fig. 12; its critical length depends on specimen geometry and decreases with increasing hole size, leading to a more brittle behaviour, see Fig. 11. The stress concentration factor and local stresses near the hole edge increase with increasing hole size and therefore, it

is less likely that local stress relief or stress redistribution can occur in such plates resulting in lower strengths. During the compression test of specimens with a large hole ($a/W > 0.4$) failure occurred at about the same time as initial cracking sounds were heard. Fig. 11 and Fig. 13 indicate that the notched compressive strength decreases as the specimen width is increased. The open hole compressive (OHC) strength for the specimen with a 50 mm \times 50 mm gauge section is lower than the 30 mm \times 30 mm specimen with the same a/W ratio as presented through Barzant's experimental results. However, no significant width effect is observed for specimens with $W \geq 50$ mm, see Fig. 13, but may need further testing to confirm this statement.

Fig. 7: Anti-buckling device for (a) 50mm \times 50mm specimen and (b) schematic diagram for analysing the anti-buckling device effect

Fig. 8: Stress distributions in a 50mm \times 50mm unnotched multidirectional composite specimen ($T300/924C, [45/-45/0/90]_{3s}$) as a function of frictional coefficient caused by the anti-buckling device.

Fig.9: Average compressive failure strengths of the multidirectional composite laminates ($T300/924C, [45/-45/0/90]_{3s}$) measured for in-plane size effect. The average strengths for 50mm \times 50mm, 70mm \times 70mm and 90mm \times 90mm specimens were corrected due to the anti-buckling device effect

Fig.10: Photographs of typical failed specimens containing an open hole

Fig. 11: Hole size effect on the strength of the T300/924C composite laminate

Fig. 12: X-ray radiographs showing compressive damage in the vicinity of an open hole (Diameter = 6.35 mm, T300/924C [+45/-45/0/90]_{3s})

Fig.13: Width effect on open hole compressive strength of the T300/924C composite laminate

Fig. 14: Stress distributions in a T300/924C orthotropic plate of finite width ($W = 30$ mm) containing a 3mm, 6mm, 9mm, 12mm, or 15mm open hole

Fig. 15: Comparison of experimental data and predicted results for the open hole compressive strength

FAILURE ANALYSIS OF OPEN HOLE SPECIMENS

Stress Distribution near An Open Hole in A Finite Width Plate

In this study, it is obtained by performing a two-dimensional finite element analysis using the FE77 package and also an approximate analytical solution by Savin. Fig. 14 illustrates the stress distributions along the transverse axis (y -axis) for a T300/924C laminate with a gauge section of 30mm x 30mm, containing a 3mm, 6mm, 9mm, 12mm and 15mm diameter hole, derived by the two methods. The agreement between the numerical and analytical solution is acceptable except for $a/W > 0.4$ at $y/W > 0.7$ due to finite width effects that are not accurately captured by Savin's method. The results indicate that the stress concentration factor increases with increasing a/W and for bigger hole sizes the material near the hole experiences higher local stress that may cause failure at lower applied loads, see experimental observations above. The SCF values could be used with the maximum stress failure criterion to estimate damage initiation. In the following paragraph a cohesive zone model is employed to estimate the notched strength using the unnotched strength σ_{un} and the laminate in-plane fracture toughness K_C

Cohesive Zone Model

In the present study, the corrected values of the unnotched strength for each specimen size and an estimated fracture toughness, $K_c = 40 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{m}$, were used to calculate the notched strength of the T300/924C laminate; further information on evaluating the K_c parameter and its effect on the notched strength can be found in reference. Open hole failure strengths predicted from the model are given in Fig. 15, where the open hole failure strength normalized by the predicted unnotched failure strength (645MPa – see Fig. 9) is plotted against the ratio of a (hole diameter) / W (specimen width). In order to normalise the experimental notched failure strength, the corrected values of the unnotched strength for each specimen size tested were used.

In the investigation of the predicted data shown in Fig. 15, the data show clear open hole size effect in the finite width plates. From the comparison of the experimental data and predicted data, the theoretical predictions are in a good agreement with the experimental measurements, less than 10% difference, Fig. 15, giving further confidence in the use of the Soutis *et al.* fracture model[8].

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this study the effect of gauge section (length \times width) was investigated on the static compressive strength of a currently used carbon fibre-epoxy system; the lay-up was a quasi-isotropic and the specimen thickness was kept constant.

For all size unnotched specimens, an anti-buckling device was mounted to avoid Euler buckling. The bigger size specimens except for the 30mm \times 30mm specimens directly contacted on the anti-buckling device in order for the specimen failure to induce to occur within the gauge length. The test results released that compressive strengths with the larger specimens are slightly higher than that of the 30mm \times 30mm specimens due to the frictional effect by bolts' joining torque in the anti-buckling device. This effect was analyzed using finite element method. It was identified that the anti-buckling device with the larger specimens causes about 7% higher compressive strength than that of the 30mm \times 30mm specimens and the measured compressive strengths were corrected by 7%. From these data, it

appears that the unnotched strength does not depend on specimen size. Failure is matrix dominated and occurs due to fibre microbuckling in the 0° plies, which is a fibre instability failure mode. The initiation of this failure mode is greatly dependent on initial fibre waviness, which highlights the importance of manufacturing processes. Fibre waviness may worsen with increasing thickness so further work is required to investigate this effect.

The introduction of open holes causes severe reduction in the compressive strength of the T300/924C laminate. However, the composite system is not ideally brittle and some stress redistribution occurs around the hole before failure. X-ray radiography and scanning electron microscopy reveal that damage in the form of fibre microbuckling, delamination and matrix cracking, occurs in the vicinity of the hole prior to catastrophic fracture. This damage reduces the stress concentration factor at the edge of the hole and delays final failure to higher applied stresses. The results indicate that the notched compressive strength decreases with increasing hole diameter or specimen width (for same a/W ratio). However, no significant width effect is observed when $W \geq 50$ mm. The effects of the hole size and specimen width upon the compressive strength are predicted with reasonable accuracy by the Soutis *et al.* cohesive zone model. The model takes as its input the compressive unnotched strength and the fracture toughness of the laminate that can be measured or estimated from a fibre microbuckling model.

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